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LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF PARENT - CHILD SPEECH IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Annotation. This thesis deals with cultural features of parent and child speech in English literary texts and the problems of translation of these features to Uzbek language. A person's relatives, whether they are near or distant, have a certain thing his place in life. Kinship can be divided into blood relatives and relatives according to the degree of closeness. In this study, we aimed to do a comparative analysis of the relations between this type of relatives in the English and Uzbek languages. Family, families and kinship relations form the culture of the people and show its specific characteristics, and help to realize the national, linguistic image of the world on a large scale. The issue of family relations applies not only to sociology, but also to cultural and linguistic studies. It is natural to approach this problem from the point of view of linguistic and cultural studies. Linguistic units with a cultural-national character attract the attention of researchers with the study of linguistics. Translating literary texts, however, is not an easy task because it

certainly poses many problems for the translator who should be bilingual and bicultural if needed.

Key words: Linguocultural features, parent-child speech, linguistic culture

Approaches to the study of parent-child relationships are made from different perspectives, such as psychiatry and psychology. Sociologists, psychologists, sociolinguists and linguists for many years. Based on literary texts, mass communication publications, poems, Lavitsky describes the concept of “Children” of the Vitebsk region of Belarus in his scientific article. It explores children's lives from different perspectives, in which the role and place of parents is inevitable. Go Pintin approaches this issue as a family tradition, comparing Chinese and Russian parentchild relationships based on proverbs and sayings of the two languages. Biktagirova makes a comparative analysis of the issue of the concept of “Family” based on the materials of different languages systematically, such as English, Turkish and other languages. The diversity of languages, the variety of cultures and necessity of communications in human life caused translation to be a very effective factor in communicating, exchanging cultures, and knowledge.⁶¹ A number of studies have specifically addressed the importance of a parent - child relationship in the family. Despite the love of parents, they need to develop the skills of communicating with children and listening to them. The diversity of languages, the variety of cultures and necessity of communications in human life caused translation to be a very effective factor in communicating, exchanging cultures, and knowledge.⁶²

For children, the family is one of the main places of residence, development and psychological formation. It is a family that creates relationships between family members. Parents are the main sources of interpersonal development for their children (parent-child relationships, parent-ancestor relationships). This issue has attracted attention the attention of many scientists. So what is the relationship

⁶¹ Bush, P. (1998) “Literary Translation.” In: M. Baker, ed. Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies, London: Routledge

⁶² Chaal, Houaria.(2018). The cultural Constraints in Literary work. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

between parents and children? The relationship between parents and children is explained by Dunn and Brown.⁶³ As they noted, this form of relationship allows the child to understand emotions, because in the conversation when a small child tells his parents about various situations, stories full of joy, surprise and other emotions, emotional speech between parents and children is inevitable. Another scientist says that a sincere conversation in the parent-child relationship guarantees respect, trust and security for the child's psychology.

For many years, in Uzbek culture even in the marriage of a son, obtaining the consent of the father, a marriage without the consent of the father or a white blessing is not a happy marriage.⁶⁴ To be degraded or to be disgraced among the people, and for this reason to marry a son or a daughter to marry a family of prospective brides-to-be. In the work of Abdulla Kadiri called "Last days" there were given statements which reflect the role of father in a family such as "Does the father rule in the family?" or "Does the father take care of everything in the family?" It has become a habit to be questioned with words like "Son, whether you hear it or not, we are a scapegoat for you we have done work". In this expression, we can understand from the words of Yusufbek Hoji, Otabek's father, that the most important thing in the family is the father saying, because the son does not double the word of the father, the father marries his son from the family he considers worthy. At this point, we can observe that the situation is completely different in English families, where a boy or a girl in the family can get married whenever and whoever they want. In English families, too, fathers try to raise their children well, pay special attention to their talents or abilities, and try to take their place in society according to their talents or abilities.

Communication depends on two interlocutors and under no circumstances should Hisham Altalib, Abdul Hamid Abu Sulaiman and Omar Altalib be interrupted. Relationship quality largely depends on parent-child communication,

⁶³ Dunn and Brown (1998), *Meaning based-translation: Guide to cross-language equivalence*, University of Richmond, Virginia

⁶⁴ N. Brooks, (1968), *Cultural features in the literary work*. In JM Valdes *Culture bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

parental feelings of burden Moore, Christine and Busby, Andrea and Bundy, Tawana.⁶⁵ Another group of scientists supports the idea that the earlier the parent-child relationship is formed, the more successful the relationship is established, because communication is related to emotional survival, understanding feelings.

However, parents differ in the extent to which they discuss feelings with their children. Insecure parents versus secure parents may feel more comfortable discussing positive and negative emotions with their children, and as a result, children of secure parents may have more opportunities to discuss and reflect on feelings. Although most of the work on predicting children's emotion understanding has focused on both parental characteristics such as depression.

In conclusion we can say that the parent-child relationship is culturally specific and reflected in the linguistic representation of the world mainly in proverbs. Examining the different manifestations of parent-child relationships in English and Uzbek cultures showed that cultural factors play an important role in this matter.

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